

MEASUREMENT OF RESIDUAL STRAIN OF PERFORATED WOVEN CARBON-EPOXY COMPOSITES BY MICRO-RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

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SUMMARY: Micro-Raman spectroscopy was used as a quantitative means of characterizing residual strain in a damaged composite specimen. Raman shift is shown to be inversely proportional to the strain in tension and proportional to strain in compression. The results show that in woven specimens, the crack also appears crossed and propagates in both directions probably due to the woven nature of the specimen. It is conceivable that the cracks first initiate at the point of intersections of the weave, and move in both directions. It also shows that the point of intersection of the weave will also indicate the point of weakest or highest strain for the same energy and exhibits a wave nature in the strain profile.

KEYWORDS: Residual Strain, micro-Raman spectroscopy, carbon-epoxy composites, perforation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, the use of micro-Raman spectroscopy for characterization of composite materials has received some attention in the literature. Raman spectroscopy has been applied successfully in studies of the following: the effect of matrix cracking during the deformation of composite materials [1]; failure mechanisms of unidirectional carbon fiber-epoxy composites [2]; investigation of the micromechanics of two-dimensional carbon fiber/epoxy micro-composites [3]; micromechanical investigation of unidirectional carbon-epoxy composites [4]; stress concentration phenomena due to fiber failure resulting in fiber-fiber interaction in graphite-epoxy composites [5]; and load transfer in a short-fiber, high-modulus epoxy composite as a function of angle loading [6]. While the conclusions of the above studies were based on the analysis of the observed Raman spectra, the studies did not provide concrete correlation between the observed atomic vibrations and the dynamics of fracture. This is significant because a more accurate understanding of material behavior is needed to advance the search for new composite materials. While most of the recent Raman applications focused mainly on fiber-reinforced composites, little work has been done on graphite-epoxy woven composites. We propose to cut through the specimen by using previous techniques and measure the Raman spectra from the exposed fiber-matrix interface or fiber-fiber interface. The dominant failure mechanism in laminated composites is interlaminar delamination. To fully understand this mode and other modes of composite failures, the interfacial measurement characteristic of the fracture surface is very important. Chohan et al. [3] investigated interfacial measurement and fracture characteristics of

composites using Raman spectroscopy and demonstrated that stress concentration exists in regions of fiber break, and regions in which inter fiber distance is very small. Micro-Raman spectroscopy has also been applied to evaluations of stress intensity factors and fracture toughness measurements [7]. Recent research has shown that this stress concentration in tension is different from that of compression [5]. The modes of fracture (mode I tearing, mode II shearing, and mode III twisting) can be differentiated by the energy levels of tension/compression, bending, and shearing/twisting. We believe the differences are due to variations in the materials atomic deformation, which can be studied by measuring the atomic vibration energy using the proposed system.

As part of the SOW for this project, the University of Pittsburgh proposes laser-based quantitative means of analyzing the surface damage to gain a better understanding of material residual dynamic structural properties and behavior at failure transition or interphase zones. The major task is to develop a quantitative means of profiling the residual strain and so characterize the perforation deformation of composite materials at critical failure transition zones such as the critical (penetration) limit velocity region.

In Raman phenomena, an incident light is scattered inelastically at a frequency higher (energy is gained) or lower than (energy is lost) the incoming photon source. A Micro-Raman spectroscopy technique employs Raman spectroscopy with about 1 μm resolution. The energy lost or gained is equal to the Raman shift or vibration energy of the material. For the purpose of this investigation, we will define strain intensity as Raman shift in wave numbers. Materials, because of their unique atomic and molecular makeup, have unique vibration energies that can be identified and whose behaviors can be predicted. Laser Raman spectroscopy is a reliable technique for direct measurement of fiber stress at the microscopic level based mainly on the fact that Raman frequencies of the constituent fibers are stress-strain dependent. Heat, moisture absorption, dynamic impact, or a combination of these factors result in transformation of micro-mechanical properties of composite materials in the region of damage and beyond. The materials may be toughened due to changes in phase incorporation or grain distribution. Several authors have shown that the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites are also controlled by fiber orientation, length, and the fiber-matrix interaction. This is due to the fact that the applied load is mainly carried by the fiber length and the interface, and the effective propagation of the strain on the fiber is affected by the number of fiber ends, the interface, and fiber-fiber interaction. In many crystalline or paracrystalline materials, the Raman peak position shifts linearly to lower wave numbers under tensile strain and to higher wave number under compressive strain.

2. Experimentation

The composite panels were fabricated using plain (3K yarn, 12.5 by 12.5 count, 5.7 oz/sq yd, 0.2286 mm, tensile strength 1.17 GPa, 230 GPa, Figure 1a) and 2/2 twill (3K yarn, 12.5 by 12.5 count, 194.88 g/m², 0.3175 mm, Figure 1b) weave T300B-40B-3K-Toray carbon fabric and Applied Poleramic SC-14 epoxy resin through a VARIM process [8]. The average thickness of the plain weave laminate was 1.6 mm for twill and 1.7 mm for the hybrid weave. The total thickness of the laminate and polycarbonate was 4.1 mm for the plain-weave polycarbonate, and 4.2 mm for the twill and hybrid-weave polycarbonate.

Figure 1. a) Plain weave fabric, and b) 2/2 Twill weave fabric

The perforation tests were designed to investigate the damage evolution below, at, and beyond the ballistic limit. The experimental setups that integrate all components of the system to micromechanical analysis require the samples (such as matrix resins or fibers pulled from damaged specimens) tested by the dynamic mechanical testing DMT system be transferred to the MRS system for micro-mechanical analysis. The degradation rate due to high rate loading in this case, for example, is known to depend on the chemical and physical structures, local heating, the nature of the material, the duration of induced stress, the types of additives and modifiers used, contaminants, and microbes. The basic system is configured with a true confocal microprobe for maximum spatial resolution. The system provides two interchangeable gratings for both high-resolution spectra and a fast overview function for wider wavelength ranges in one system. The appropriate holographic notch filter is incorporated into the system to enable acquisition of Raman spectra with conditions optimized for sensitivity and low frequency performance. The LabRam is delivered with a 17 mW 633 nm HeNe laser and additional lasers for other excitation wavelengths. The main excitation source for the spectrometer is a medium-power argon laser capable of delivering wavelengths of 514.5 nm, 488.0 nm, and 532 nm, and a solid-state laser with temperature control and ventilation for high stability and extended operating life. For the fastest and easiest conversion from one laser to another, a specially designed prealigned plugin module is provided, housing the appropriate filter and mirror for each laser choice. To confirm the correct alignment of the laser, a very special feature has been incorporated. A low-power laser diode is mounted inside the spectrograph to back illuminate the entrance slit and an alignment confirmation can be initiated by computer keystroke. The complete stigmatic spectrograph, achromatic over a broad range (450 nm–1.05 microns), is equipped with two interchangeable gratings for variable spectral resolution. The 1800 g/mm grating provides a spectral resolution of $\sim 2.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in three pixels using the standard HeNe laser and one optional argon laser. The second grating is chosen for a wide Raman spectroscopic overview in one scan or for recording laser fluorescence spectra over a broad wavelength range. The LabRam system is equipped with a rugged, compact, air-cooled CCD made by ISA. The CCD is an extremely sensitive ease-of-use detector and represents state-of-the-art technology in multichannel, two-dimensional detectors. It exhibits exceptionally low dark currents as well as a high sensitivity and high dynamic range. The sample (solid or liquid in a vial) is placed in the xyz plane of the microscope stage and can be easily adjusted. This macrosampling device mounts on the turret of the microscope via a standard microscope objective thread.

Thus, Raman spectroscopy is used in this experiment to measure the Raman spectra for selected specimens penetrated in the vicinity of penetration limit using conical hemispherical, spherical protruding, and hemispherical protruding. The window of the Raman machine was set at 1579.92 cm^{-1} to scan for the Raman signal of the graphite fiber in the specimens. The laser was used as the light source because it provides a narrow beam, high-intensity light source and blue-green excitation line. The data was also plotted using graphic computer software. The expectation of the shift (wavelength number) change is not linear with respect to strain. In tension, the strain increases and the shift decrease such that:

$$\Delta f \propto \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where, Δf = Wavelength number (cm^{-1}), and ε = Strain (percent). The Raman shift is determined for each woven graphite-epoxy specimen of varying thickness by taking the shift reading on the transverse side by cutting the samples along the x-axis.

The experiment was designed to determine the variation of residual strain for through-the-thickness compression (penetrator entrance side), tension (the exit side), and in the traverse direction (in-plane). Each specimen was marked along the diameter on the surface of the composite disk, as shown from the X-Y intersect point (Figure 2). To establish the baseline for the real specimens, Raman spectra of undamaged specimens were obtained for each sample thickness. For the transverse side, a specimen holder was designed to hold the samples on the Raman machine. Samples were picked randomly and the reading of the shift and the intensity was recorded in the log notebook. The outcome of this experiment meets the hypothesis expectation.

Location	Measured Distance (mm)
2	6
1	16
0	18
-1	24
-2	30

Figure 2. Experimental configuration for obtaining strain intensity profile from the (a) surface, and (b) Internal traverse (in-plane) surface of damaged specimen

3. Experimental Results and Discussions

The photographs in Fig. 3 reveal the variation of the damage event as a function of impact energy for $\frac{1}{4}$ protruding spherical-nose and $\frac{1}{4}$ conical hemi-spherical-nose penetrators. Rear surface cracks on the woven specimen were first observed when the impact energy was 39J. Since a surface crack is usually initiated before perforation by the penetrator is achieved, the “ballistic limit” will be higher than the surface crack initiation velocity when defined in terms of the traverse velocity of the penetrator nose. Perforation was achieved at 68J. For approximately the same damage threshold levels, the conical hemi-spherical-nosed penetrator appears to cause more pronounced damage than the protruding spherical-nosed penetrator.

Fig. 3 Penetration of woven specimens using $\frac{1}{4}$ (a) a conical hemi spherical- nosed and (b) a protruding spherically-nosed penetrator.

Figures 4-7 show the Raman spectra with intensity plotted in arbitrary units (counts/s). The peak of the spectrum is proportional to the concentration of atomic species giving the Raman frequency. For this experiment, the shift from graphite is most dominant and resolved. The figure compares the spectrum of an undamaged specimen with the compression side of a damaged specimen. The typical shift of graphite is at 1580 cm^{-1} . This was observed using our setup to be at $1605\pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The peak of the damaged specimen can be seen in Figure 4 to be shifted ± 5 wave numbers to the left. The vertical line is to guide your eyes. Figure 5 also compares the tension side to the undamaged spectrum and shows that the peak is also shifted, but this time to the right. The complete strain intensity profile is shown in Figure 6. The data is obtained as previously described by scanning across the specimen surface around the damage zone, as in Figure 4. Comparison of these profiles shows a definite difference between strain distributions in compression. The profile indicates a local minimum around the point of highest strain corresponding to the specimen center around the point of impact. There is also the presence of alternation of the smaller lows and highs. This may be due to alternate regions of the intersections of woven fibers.

GW16-1 (L18 compression)
Delta F=1608.75 cm⁻¹

(a)

GW16-40 no impact test
Delta F=1605 cm⁻¹

GW16-1 (L12 compression)
Delta F=1600.03 cm⁻¹

(b)

Figure 4. Comparison of Raman spectrum for 16-Layer Sample a) Compression and tension Sides at center location b) Compression side damage compared to (1)undamaged sample

GW16-17 (L18 tension), Delta F=1586.92 cm⁻¹

(a)

Figure 5. Comparison of Raman spectrum of undamaged and damaged samples for 16-layer a) tension side at center location b) Tension side damage compared to undamaged sample

(a)

Figure 6. Strain Intensity Profile for 16-Layer Sample for a) Tension and b) Compression

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Strain intensity profile for a) Protruding spherical, and b) Conical hemispherical penetrator at varying sample strains (%)

Figure 6 compares the strain intensity profile for both hemispherical and spherical penetrator for varying strain rates. Again, the peak shows a minimum at the center. However, the hemispherical penetrator shows a nonlocalized strain effect. The plot shows that when the shift decreases the strain increases; this can be seen very clearly with the specimens: GPW24-11, GPW24-22, GPW24-43, GPW16-36, GPW16-43, and GPW12-29 in Figure 6. In addition, from the visual observation of the specimens, the highest damage is located at the center of the composite disks. This is about 18 mm from the reference frame and matches with the above outcome. Thus, the results show the highest stress point occurs at the center point of impact of the specimen where perforation occurs. *The sinusoidal shape of some of the plots is most interesting. This suggests the way in which the layers and the matrix of the composite materials are put together.*

Figure 8 shows the comparison of the average Raman shift peak induced by changes in strain intensity for compression and tension. The results show that carbon graphite/epoxy composites have a positive wave number shift in compression compared to negative shift in tension, in agreement with typical published results [7]. This observation shows that compression-induced strain can be measured and monitored using the Raman spectroscopy technique presented in this studies. This is important in the assessment of residual strength of aged aircraft structures.

Figure 8. Variation of strain induced Raman shift averaged over all the locations with sample average strain

4. Conclusions

The conclusions from these plots are as follows:

- The results indicate that the conical hemispherical penetrator will defeat its target at a higher energy level than the spherical penetrator will. However, damage by the spherical penetrator is highly localized because of the penetrator shape.
- As the size of the penetrator is increased, the penetration and perforation threshold energies increase significantly. At the same energy level, the larger size penetrator-nose will deliver more energy to the target. The size of the nose contact area is more significant in energy delivery than the shape of the penetrator itself.
- Micro-Raman spectroscopy is a reliable quantitative means of characterizing residual strain in a damaged specimen. The strain intensity profile shows a definite difference between strain distribution in compression and tension. Raman shift is shown to be inversely proportional to the strain in tension and proportional to strain in compression.
- Profiles indicate a local minimum around the point of highest strain corresponding to the specimen center and the point of impact.

- The results show that in woven specimens, the crack also appears crossed and propagates in both directions probably due to the woven nature of the specimen. It is conceivable that the cracks first initiate at the point of intersection of the weave, and move in both directions.
- It also shows that the point of intersection of the weave will also indicate the point of weakest or highest strain for the same energy and exhibits a wave nature in the strain profile.

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